

Treatment of Gingival Recession with Connective Tissue Graft with a Coronally Advanced Flap: A Case Report

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Citation: Manju Krishnan, Mohanasateesh, Anitha Balaji. Treatment of Gingival Recession with Connective Tissue Graft with a Coronally Advanced Flap: A Case Report. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(12):1-5.

Received Date: 26 December, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 30 December, 2024; **Published Date:** 31 December, 2024

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ABSTRACT

The normal position of the gingiva is affected by gingival recessions, which also expose the tooth root and are commonly accompanied with unsightly aesthetics and dentin hypersensitivity. The coronally advanced flap technique for root covering is a periodontal plastic surgery operation that is recommended for the treatment of gingival recessions. Within this case study, following a six-month follow-up, we present the clinical results of a root-covering procedure performed on lower incisors with gingival recession. A 30-year-old patient who had Miller's class I gingival recession on the vestibular surfaces of teeth 31 underwent a one-stage surgical procedure employing the coronally advanced approach in conjunction with a largely epithelialized connective tissue graft. After a six-month follow-up, this treatment achieved 100% root coverage.

INTRODUCTION

Gingival recession is a common finding in everyday clinical practice ^[1]. According to the American Academy of Periodontology, the gingiva migrates to an area near the cemento-enamel junction ^[2]. Periodontal disease, forceful tooth brushing, inappropriate frenal attachment, inflammation, insufficient flossing, incorrect occlusal connections, and other factors are the most common etiological reasons. The exposed root surface is covered with soft tissue during mucogingival surgery to treat gingival recessions. This improves aesthetics, widens the surrounding gingiva, and lowers tooth sensitivity ^[3]. The Connective Tissue Graft (CTG) is recognized as the gold standard of soft tissue grafting procedures because of its high predictability and attractive results. Despite the excellent cosmetic outcomes of this operation, a suitable donor site is important because root coverage (RC), which has been found to range from 69% to 97% in most trials, is needed ^[4]. The original publication by Edel (1974) described one of the unique techniques for harvesting a free CTG, which involved making a three-sided "trapdoor" incision on the palate ^[5] and

then performing a coronal advanced flap, which was done first.^[6] Either a one-stage or two-stage technique can be used. Between the flap and the root surface, a connective tissue graft—an autologous tissue taken from the palate—is positioned to receive a twofold blood supply from the underlying periosteum.

CASE REPORT

Mrs. Gomathi, a female patient, was 30 years old when she visited the outpatient department of periodontics at Sree Balaji Dental College and Hospital. Her main concern was that her gums had been receding in the area around her lower front teeth for the past two months. The patient had a history of gums that bled when they were brushed. The patient had no systemic illnesses or relevant medical history.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

In the face aspect of the mandibular anterior region, which was chosen for treatment, clinical examination revealed grade 1 mobility in teeth 31 and Miller class I gingival recession in respect to teeth 31. The patient maintained poor dental hygiene. Due to stress from occlusion, there was recession in the lower anterior region on soft tissue examination.

Figure 1 A) preoperative image reveals Miller's class 1 in relation to 31 B) reveals 4mm (about 0.16 in) of buccal recession in relation to 31.

TREATMENT

Correcting the occlusal position and performing mucogingival surgery to completely cover the roots were the main objectives of the therapy. The study of occlusal contacts in relation to identifying occlusal inconsistencies in the teeth led to the elimination of premature connections. The patient made no mention of their parafunctional habits. The patient received oral hygiene advice before the mucogingival surgery and underwent prophylaxis, coronal debridement, scaling, and root planning. If the patient had less than 10% periodontal site bleeding on probing and plaque index, and less than 20% according to the O'Leary index, mucogingival surgery was done^[7].

Armamentarium

COEPAK periodontal dressing, BP handle, BP blade no. 15, gauze sponges, and normal saline.

Surgical Procedure

Prior to the procedure, the perioral area was cleaned with a 10% betadine solution, and the patient was instructed to rinse her mouth out with 0.12% chlorhexidine. Scaling and root planning were done to get rid of the plaque deposits. Then, two vertical incisions are made at least one papilla mesial and distal from the area of recession to raise a partial-thickness flap. To bio-modify the root surface and eliminate the smear layer, tetracycline was administered to condition the root surface [8]. A local anesthetic medication is used to numb the area of the hard palate where the connective tissue transplant must be extracted. Using both horizontal and vertical incisions, the palate is used to harvest the connective tissue transplant. To make graft removal easier, two vertical cuts are now performed at the ends of the horizontal incisor. The connective tissue graft is now separated from the bone using a periosteal elevator. On the harvested graft, all adipose and glandular tissue has been eliminated. Primary closure involves suturing the palatal wound. A sulcular incision is created with a 15-cm blade around the teeth next to the recession to create a tunnel pouch to receive the graft. Regarding 31, the graft is immediately applied to the denuded root surface after being sutured at the midline level with a single 5-0 nylon suture. A partial-thickness flap is then placed over the graft's exterior. As it is essential for graft survival, the flap should cover at least half to two thirds of the graft. After that, a periodontal pack should be applied to the area.

Figure 2 A) intrasulcular incision made and reflected with periosteal elevator. B) thread is placed around the cervical portion of the teeth involving 41,31,32. C) a thin membrane of aluminum foil is placed and marked over the site to be harvested. D) a harvested connective tissue graft. E) View of the recipient bed with periosteum and mucosal flap left in place. F) Fixation of connective tissue graft onto the surface to be covered.

Figure 3 A) wound closure with horizontal compression sutures B) Suturing and complete coverage of CTG C) Suturing and complete coverage of CTG D) 6th month postoperative E) 6th month post operative (recipient site)

DISCUSSION

Gingival recession causes poor aesthetics, pain, and sensitivity. Numerous surgical techniques have been employed to treat gingival recession issues. They also involve keratinized tissue-widening root-covering procedures [9]. Other indications for root covering procedures include root sensitivity and altering the architecture of marginal soft tissue to aid plaque control. Techniques for root covering are a crucial part of the treatment for gingival recession [10]. In this instance, the connective tissue graft (CTG) procedure was selected due to the next tooth's favorable periodontal state, which included enough keratinized gingiva and bone height. For patients with a single or many recessions, the coronally advanced flap and tunnelling procedures in combination with a connective tissue graft are thought to be the most dependable therapy options. The benefit of this operation is that thicker gingival margins that are more secure and have a probability of "creeping reattachment" are established after healing. Multiple gingival recessions were treated by Zabalegui et al. (1999) by making a tunnel underneath the recession-affected areas to accept the connective tissue transplant [11]. According to a systematic review and meta-analysis that examined the long-term effects of untreated facial gingival recession, subjects with good oral hygiene are highly likely to experience an increase in recession depth over the course of long-term follow-up [12]. Agudio et al. (2016) compared the treated

sites to homologous contralateral sites that had a thin gingival phenotype, either with recessions or without. At the conclusion of the follow-up period, the recession's severity had decreased in 83% of the 64 treated locations and had gotten worse in 48% of the 64 untreated sites. A study in the literature compared coronally advanced flaps with porcine collagen matrix to coronally advanced flaps with connective tissue grafts for the treatment of gingival recession defects; both treatment methods led to significantly less recession at 12 months ^[13].

CONCLUSION

In this case report, we show how wide and deep gingival recessions that affect aesthetic areas can be treated with a one-stage surgical strategy that combines the coronally advanced method with a CTG that is partially epithelialized. In actuality, the successful treatment of this case did not necessitate the use of a two-step approach that involved increasing the width of the keratinized gingiva in the first stage and covering the roots in the second stage. 100% root coverage was achieved in this case with long-term stability and attractiveness.

REFERENCE

1. Jean-Claude Imber and Adrian Kasaj, Treatment of Gingival Recession: When and How? Int Dent J. 2021;71(3):178-187.
2. The American Academy of Periodontology, Glossary of Periodontal Terms, 4th edition. Chicago: The American Academy of Periodontology; 2001:1-56.
3. Claudia Amaya Bautista, Angelica M. Cardenas, Emilio A Cafferata, Ronaldo Vernal, Treatment of a single gingival recession with a subepithelial connective tissue graft with a double papilla flap. SAGE Open Med Case Rep.2022.
4. Komal puri, Ashish Kumar, Manish Khatri, 44- year journey of palatal connective tissue graft harvest: A narrative review, Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology,
5. Sonja Böhm, Dietmar Weng, Jörg Meyle, Connective Tissue Grafts in Periodontal Surgery.
6. Giovanni Zuchelli, Lorenzo Tavelli, Martina Stefanini, Shayan Barootchi, Hom-Lay Wang; The coronally advanced flap technique revisited: Treatment of peri-implant soft tissue dehiscence, Int J Oral Implantology(Berl). 2021;14(4):351-365.
7. O'Leary TJ, Drake RB, Naylor JE. The plaque control record. J Periodontal 1972; 43: 38–38.
8. Kratee Sharma, Ellora Madan, Manvi Agarwal and Zaby Fathima: Tetracycline as a root bio modifying agent, International Journal of Current Research, 7(11): 23277-23280, November,2015.
9. Hamdan Alghamdi, Nadir Babay, Anil Sukumaran; Surgical management of gingival recession: A clinical update; Saudi Dent J. 2009;21(2): 83-94.
10. Mirsad Shkreta, Aneta Atanasovska-Stojanovska , Blerta Dollaku; Exploring the Gingival Recession Surgical Treatment Modalities: A Literature Review Maced J Med Sci 2018; 6(4): 698-708.

11. Shaik Sameera, * Medandrao Nagasri, Pavuluri Aravind Kumar, Pantareddy Indeevar, Kalapala Raviraj, and S.V.V.S. Musalaiah; Comparison of two surgical techniques in the treatment of multiple gingival recessions sandwiched with a combination of A-PRF and L-PRF Saudi Dent J. 2018; 30(3): 183–189.
12. EunJin Ahn¹ and Hyun Kang²; Introduction to systematic review and meta-analysis; KoreanJAnesthesiol. 2018;71(2):103–112.
13. Marlena Pedowska,¹ Marta Prokop,² Renata Chałas; The Use of Collagen Matrix in the Treatment of Gingival Recession—A Pilot Study; J Pers Med 2022; 12(11): 1902.